

SOLID MECHANICS-BASED SIMULATION OF COMPOSITE FORMING WITH STRESS RELAXATION IN THE DRY FABRIC REINFORCEMENT AND RESIN CURING

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1 General Introduction

Woven fabric preforms are the reinforcing agent of several high performance parts in composite industries. In the dry form, they are formed into 3D surface geometries and consolidated with a matrix material using processes such as resin transfer moulding (usually for thermosets), thermostamping (for thermoplastics), and compression moulding [1]. Woven fabrics are composed of two main structural directions (warp and weft) which can have different relative angles during forming due to shear. The latter is the main deformation mode in forming fabrics and has a significant effect on the final (effective) material properties of the composite part, as well as the consolidation time during moulding by means of associated factors such as permeability [2].

Earlier solid-mechanics based numerical studies have been conducted on the simulation of forming process of dry fabric reinforcements; e.g., [1], [3]. These models have mostly treated the process up to a (quasi)static or dynamic deformation of the dry fabric. It has been reported that in practice after resin cures there can be undesired deformations such as warpage and wrinkling that prevent producing net-shape products [4], [5], [6]. In fact, although a fabric material may initially be perfectly draped around a mould with no wrinkles or defects, after the fabric-matrix consolidation and de-moulding of the part, deviations from the mould geometry can be present and even lead to discarding the part by manufacturer. There may be a variety of sources to this dimensional infidelity, including manufacturing

variabilities [4], thermal effects, chemical phase changes in the matrix as well as tool-part interactions [5]. Including all these sources in a single simulation model can be very complex and/or computationally expensive. However, looking at the effect of individual sources and studying some level of interactions between them can provide engineers with an initial insight toward proper ways to reduce dimensional problems in the final products.

The aim of this article is to study the effect of two factors during the simulation of forming process of woven fabric reinforcements. The first one is the curing of the resin after the dry fabric is shaped into the mould. The second factor is an effect that has been rarely addressed for the forming process of dry fabrics: the stress relaxation in the dry fabric itself. To this end, two separate sets of simulations (called case studies 1 and 2) have been performed using compression moulding of a hemisphere part. Both effects are linked to stresses than can form during draping stage of forming, and simulated using an equivalent solid-mechanics based modeling framework for fast and yet effective preliminary sensitivity analyses.

2 Forming of Textile Composites

Textile composite parts are often manufactured by draping layers of dry or pre-impregnated preforms (mostly fabrics) into a 3D mould surface and then curing/consolidating the polymer resin around the reinforcements to form the matrix and provide a solid state of the composite part. Forming fabric reinforcements into a mould shape can be achieved

via different methods [6]. The use of a compression punch is one of the widespread methods used for both thermoset and thermoplastic matrices [7]. During the compression moulding of a fiber-reinforced composite, the fabric is first draped into a preheated mould by applying force on the punch. The next step is the consolidation/curing of the resin under pressure and temperature to form the part. The third step includes the removal of the punch and demoulding the part. Figure 1 shows the geometry of a punch-die set used for this study, and Figure 2 shows the steps that a typical composite material undergoes under this process.

The initial stage (draping) can induce internal stresses in the fiber yarns, and potentially some residual stress in the final part. More specifically, this stress state may or may not recover after removing the punch force and could result in undesirable deformations such as warpage after demoulding. Another interesting phenomenon that occurs during this process, particularly for the thermosetting composites, is the continued advancement of cure in parts that are taken prematurely out of the mould. This effect can increase the stiffness of the matrix over time and accordingly induce further residual stresses or even deformation during post-moulding stages (assembly, transportation, etc). The case studies here aim at the variation of the above type of residual stresses as the resin cures (case study 1) and as the reinforcing fabric relaxes (case study 2).

3 Case Study 1: Simulating the Forming Process with a Curing Resin

A simplified numerical approach is considered to simulate the compression moulding process in Fig. 2 following the three stages of the manufacturing. For the first stage, it is assumed that the forming material (reinforcement) is made of shell elements with a non-orthogonal constitutive behavior to represent the true nature of woven fabrics [8]. The shear and transverse stiffness of fabrics is very low compared to their axial stiffness in tension, and this should be taken into account when assigning material properties in the fabric models. In the second stage, after draping the fabric into the mould shape, all the effective stiffness values in the weft and warp directions are increased as a function of

time to mimic the consolidation/curing of the resin. Eventually, in the last stage, the punch is retracted and the external force is removed from the composite part. It is expected that the combination of residual stresses stored inside the fiber yarns due to the initial forming stage as well as the enhanced stiffness values of the fiber-matrix mixture due to the second stage (consolidation) induces deformation in the part in the last step. Resin flow, thermal and chemical effects are not considered in the model.

3.1 Dry fabric forming stage

As addressed earlier, simulating the forming of dry fabrics is one of the challenging topics in the field due to their particular multi-scale material behavior nature. There are different approaches suggested for this type of simulations, among which the macro-level approach is most common and computationally effective for large simulations [1], which was also selected here. In this approach, a conventional shell model is initially selected to represent the fabric material. However, material properties of the shell needed to be modified to represent a non-orthogonal material model behaviour that tracks the direction of yarns and establishes the correct structural directions along warp and weft yarns during forming. More closely, stiffness values along warp and weft as well as the trellising/shear stiffness between yarns should be calculated in the fabric local (non-orthogonal) coordinate system and then transferred to the regular stress values of the shell model in a global system [8]. The commercial Finite Element (FE) package, Abaqus [9] was used in the current study to apply the above transformations. Customized fabric constitutive models (e.g., nonlinear elastic) can also be defined using a VFABRIC subroutine in Abaqus [9]. Using this subroutine, a constitutive model from a previous research [8] on a glass/PP prepreg was implemented. Details of the model can be found in [8]. In summary,

$$\begin{aligned} \{d\sigma\}_{3 \times 1} &= [C]_{3 \times 3} \cdot \{d\varepsilon\}_{3 \times 1} \quad (1) \\ C_{11} &= \frac{16000}{0.9 + 7e^{-300\bar{\varepsilon}^+}} \quad (\text{MPa}) \\ C_{12} &= 2200e^{-73\bar{\varepsilon}^+} \sin(960\bar{\varepsilon}^+ + 4.1) + 70 \quad (\text{MPa}) \\ C_{22} &= C_{11}; \quad C_{21} = C_{12} \end{aligned}$$

where,

$$\bar{\varepsilon}^+ = \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}} \sqrt{(\varepsilon_1^+)^2 + (\varepsilon_2^+)^2 + (\varepsilon_1^+)(\varepsilon_2^+)} \quad (2)$$

$$\varepsilon_i^+ = \begin{cases} \varepsilon_i & \varepsilon_i > 0 \\ 0 & \varepsilon_i \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

ε_i , σ_i , $d\varepsilon_i$ and $d\sigma_i$ are the engineering strain and nominal stress and their increments along the warp and weft directions for $i=\{1,2\}$, respectively; ε_3 , σ_3 , $d\varepsilon_3$ and $d\sigma_3$ are the shear angle and shear stress and their increments. And C_{ij} are the stiffness values that relate the above-mentioned stress and strain components. Figure 3a shows the shape of the fabric after forming into the mould.

3.2 Consolidation stage

At this stage the material is held inside the closed mould while the curing is progressed. This is simulated in the solid mechanics-based model by gradually increasing the stiffness values of the shell material to the level of consolidated yarns (which is a mixture of fibers and matrix). More specifically, the material properties of Polypropylene (PP) matrix with a 30% volume fraction were added to the stiffness values of the composite shell over time (Table 1). Figure 4 shows the schematic of the material stiffness change with time during the entire forming process. Figure 3b illustrates the state of the composite part at the end of the consolidation stage. As it can be seen from the contours in this figure, there are no notable changes in the fabric trellising (change of angle between warp and weft yarns). In more realistic simulation cases, when resin flow/thermal/chemical reaction effects are included in a model, more notable changes of trellising angle could be expected at this intermediate stage of forming.

3.3 Punch retraction stage

The last step after consolidation is extracting the part. During this step, retracting the punch to its original position induces a new state of residual stresses in the composite. This is due to the fact that fibers in the yarn were in tension from the punch force during the initial forming stage; in the current case yarns have experienced a strain level in the order of $5m\varepsilon$ in the draping stage. After retracting the punch that

tension could be removed if the fabric was dry and yarns were free to move. However, the fibers are now bonded to the matrix and cannot freely move to release this stress. Therefore, they induce some compression on the matrix while they are in a lower state of tension. This residual state of stress distribution can force the material to deform and cause a deformation in the final part. Figure 3c demonstrates the state of the composite shear strain after retracting the punch. Compared to Figure 3b, no notable angle changes in the direction of yarns can be seen. Looking at the displacement of the part along the direction of the punch (normal to the initial plane of the fabric), however, a more significant effect is noticed in the order of 2mm (Figure 5). Nonetheless, because of the simple geometry of the hemisphere dome and the fact that blank holder is not applying any force in the current simulation, there is not much tension induced in the yarns in the draping stage. In order to illustrate the effect of higher yarn tensions by means of a more complex geometry or stiffer yarns, another simulation with a fictitious axial stiffness of 9.0 GPa in tension (and 0.9 GPa in compression) and 5.0 MPa in shear was run. Results of the latter simulation were added in Figure 5 and marked as stiff material.

4 Case Study 2: Testing and Simulating the Stress Relaxation in Fiber Reinforcing Fabrics

The woven fabric dry prepreg used in this case is a TWINTEx[®] balanced plain weave, which is composed of yarns made of comingled E-glass and Polypropylene (PP) fibers with a glass weight fraction of 70%. Figure 6 shows the outcome of a uniaxial tension test as well as a shear frame test on the fabric at room temperature, including the relaxation zone after the crosshead displacement is fixed at the end of quasi-static test. The observed high relaxation behavior must be related to the polymeric nature of the constituent materials in the fabric (E-Glass and PP). Especially for the thermoplastic matrix (PP), extended studies are present in the literature on its creep and stress relaxation, which are significant even at room temperature [10]. Glass is also an amorphous (non-crystalline) solid material and can be polymeric (such as acrylic glass, polycarbonate, polyethylene terephthalate), and hence contributing to the overall viscoelastic behavior of the composite. To

investigate the latter contribution more closely, Figure 7 shows the results of creep tests on the same glass/PP (70% E-glass, 30% PP) sample as well as a pure dry E-glass (100% glass) plain weave. Both samples were loaded slowly and held under a constant axial force of 100 N, while changes in strain value were recorded. Digital Image Correlation (DIC) was used for monitoring the strain in the region of interest which is the entire area colored by contours in Figure 8. It is worth adding that the stress relaxation can also partly be due to micro-level fiber movements in twisted filaments of the yarns.

The measured relaxation of stress in the woven fabric reinforcements expands over a wide range of time and can possibly change the residual stress state and relative angle of fibers during composite forming. Also, it has been proven that the tensioning of yarns can have considerable influence on the shear stiffness of fabrics [11]. Hence, one can argue that the relaxation in shear and axial stress components of the fabric reinforcement and their coupling can contribute to the changes in the final composite properties and dimensions in a complex manner. The next section of this article investigates this stress relaxation effect during the same forming process presented in the previous section; however the tension-shear coupling effect is ignored in this particular study for simplicity (see [12] for more detailed discussions).

4.1 Forming simulation with fabric stress relaxation

For the tested TWINTEX[®] fabric, a shell model was selected similar to the simulation in Section 3. The viscoelastic material properties were added to the FE code via a VFABRIC subroutine. The Zener viscoelastic constitutive model (standard linear solid model shown in Figure 9), was used to represent the stress relaxation in each yarn direction as well as the fabric shear. The formulation of the stress response in this model is as follows [13]:

$$\dot{\sigma}_{ii} + \frac{\sigma_{ii}}{\eta_{ten}} = (E_1 + E_2) \dot{\epsilon}_{ii} + \frac{E_1}{\eta_{ten}} \epsilon_{ii} \quad (4)$$

$$\dot{\tau}_{12} + \frac{\tau_{12}}{\eta_{sh}} = (G_1 + G_2) \dot{\gamma}_{12} + \frac{G_1}{\eta_{sh}} \gamma_{12} \quad (5)$$

where σ_{ii} and ϵ_{ii} are the nominal stress and strain along warp and weft directions for $ii = \{11, 22\}$, respectively. τ_{12} and γ_{12} are the in-plane shear stress and strain values. E_1, E_2, G_1, G_2 are different components of the material stiffness; and η_2, χ_2 are the effects from viscosity in tension and shear, respectively (Figure 9).

Unknown constants in Eqs. 4 and 5 were found (Table 2) via a manual curve fitting by making the viscoelastic model agreeable to the experimental data as shown in Figure 6. Note that in Table 2 the nonlinear behavior of the fabric has been taken into account by considering the deformation-dependent elastic moduli. Results of running the forming simulation with the above material model are illustrated in Figure 10, where the draping takes 1 second and the relaxation 0.25 second. An exponential trend of stress curves during the second stage where the mould is closed is noticeable in Figure 10. One interesting point is that the level of stress at point P1 on the part increases during the relaxation. This can refer to some further complexities of the composite behavior and perhaps the interaction between different regions of the part, taking into account the spatial distribution of initial tensions in the yarns and the following non-uniform relaxation.

5 Concluding Remarks

Forming of textile reinforcements and specifically dry fabrics is a main step in composite manufacturing. There are valuable researches in the literature on the subject of forming simulation of dry fabrics in thermo-stamping or similar manufacturing processes. However, there are other factors such as temperature and time-dependent curing of the resin, viscoelastic nature of the matrix and the dry yarns even at room temperature (which was shown here via stress relaxation and creep tests), the effect of fabric tension-shear coupling, resin flow, anisotropic thermal properties, etc., which need to be studied in more details in an integrated manner and linked to the ongoing draping simulations efforts.

The goal of this article was illustrating how simple FE models can be used to look into the effects of (1)

stiffness change during forming due to matrix consolidation and the associated dimensional instability after de-moulding; (2) viscoelastic behaviour of the fabric reinforcements. Simulations were solid mechanics-based and conducted via user defined subroutines in Abaqus. For the former effect, forming of a dry fabric using a punch induced stresses in the yarns. After injection/melt of the resin and its subsequent cure/consolidation these stresses can still exist in the fiber yarns. Therefore, there can be a residual stress component merely due to the draping process. It should also be mentioned that in the case of thermosetting composites with a partial cure after de-moulding, if during the performance life of the part the operating temperature approaches T_g of the part in manufacturing, the curing can progress and induce more deformation problems.

Regarding the second effect, stress relaxation of two commercial woven fabrics was tested and included in the forming simulation. Subsequently, stress relaxation in the yarns after the draping stage and during the matrix consolidation stage could affect the relative arrangement of fibers and the effective mechanical properties in the final part. This is potentially even more significant because of the influence of axial tension along yarns on the shear stiffness of fabrics (the tension-shear coupling effect which was not included here). Under a coupled behaviour, the relaxation of yarns axial stress after the initial forming stage decreases the shear stiffness of the fabrics, which in turn could yield some changes to the form of the draped fabric. Further investigations on the full characterization of fabrics' viscoelastic behavior (especially at elevated temperatures and under tension-shear coupling effects) may be worthwhile via numerical-experimental studies.

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Fig. 1. Geometry of the mould, punch and the fabric system considered in this study (all dimensions are in mm)

Fig. 2. Three stages in forming simulation of a hemisphere; (a) punch is going down to drape the dry fabric into the mould. (b) the resin is added and consolidated under pressure and temperature (overall material stiffness at this stage increases). (c) the punch moves back and the part can be removed from the mould.

Fig. 3. Relative shear angle between yarns at different stages of forming; (a) after punching; (b) after curing; (c) after retracting the punch

Fig. 4. Schematic of the change in the composite stiffness during different forming stages (for simplicity a linear regime for curing was assumed; however the user-subroutine can be conveniently changed to include curvilinear regimes).

Fig. 5. Vertical displacement of the fabrics in the center point as well as the selected point P1 (marked in Fig. 3a) during forming stages; the horizontal blue lines represent the net-shape (ideal) products.

Fig. 6. Viscoelastic behavior of the TWINTEX dry woven fabric at room temperature under (a) the uniaxial extension test, and (b) the shear frame test

Fig. 7. Results of the creep test on the TWINTEX[®] (PP/glass) as well as a pure E-glass plain fabric; (a) strain as a function of time; (b) the creep modulus as a function of time

Fig. 8. Applying 3D digital image correlation (DIC) to measure the average strain over the colored region during the creep tests

Fig. 9. The selected viscoelastic material model [13]

Fig. 10. The stress relaxation in two selected points of the part using the viscoelastic model for the TWINTEX[®] fabric

Table 1. Material properties of polypropylene matrix

	Material property [14]	30% equivalent used in the subroutine
E	1200 MPa	360 MPa
ν	0.3	0.3
G	462 MPa	138 MPa

Table 2. Material constants of the viscoelastic model in Fig. 9

Axial response		Shear response	
E_1	$4. + 9. \varepsilon_i^3$ GPa	G_1	$0.05 + 1.45 \gamma^2$ MPa
E_2	2 GPa	G_2	60 MPa
η_2	80×10^9	χ_2	60×10^6

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